

Macroscopic Observations on the COVID-19 Propagation in Europe During the First Year of the Pandemic

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Abstract—The propagation of the pathogen agent producing the COVID-19 pandemics has been mostly studied from a modeling point of view, where some theoretical models of infection propagation were proposed with a flourishing variety of mechanisms that were evolving as the pandemic was ongoing. The initial Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) models were enriched with additional states, such as hospitalized, in intensive care, vaccinated, etc. In most of the reported works, the contrast of the results of the models were qualitative, i.e. there was no data driven parameter tuning. This paper is about the exploration of the evidence of pathogen spatial diffusion during the year 2020 in Europe on the basis of the mortality time series published in the Our World in Data site. In this regard, we extract various features measuring the mortality time series similarity for each pair of countries in Europe. Then we examine the correlation of such measures with the geographical distance between countries, specifically the capital cities of the countries for lack of a better representation. The rationale is that countries that are far apart should have less similar time series than countries that are close geographically, as the basic mechanism of pathogen propagation was aerial, and countries had strong travel restrictions. The evidence that the pandemic pathogen propagation followed a definite spatial diffusion process is very weak at the macroscopic level.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has been characterized by many unexplained phenomena. One is how the virus propagated between countries at a time (the year 2020) when all boundaries were closed. While many studies have examined outbreaks within single countries or regions, transmission across borders—particularly in Europe—has received less attention. Europe’s different government responses created a distinct epidemiological landscape, and the interactions between neighboring nations remain poorly studied. This paper is focused on the statistical observations that can be extracted macroscopic behavior of the pandemic in European countries, namely the mortality time series. We propose a combination of time-sensitive alignment techniques (Dynamic Time Warping, Wavelet Coherence, and Cross-correlation), geospatial network modeling, and explainable AI (XAI) to study the spread of the disease. We compute similarities between mortality time series of all pairs of countries, and correlate them with the pairwise country geographical distances trying to uncover spatial trends in pandemic progression in Europe. Our work introduces a new way to study COVID-19 spread in Europe that addresses the

gaps in the literature. In fact, the entire approach tries to find statistical evidence sustaining the hypothesis of the pathogen spatial diffusion by person to person propagation.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II examines prior research on COVID-19 transmission dynamics. Section III outlines our methodology, covering the explanation of the data sources, similarity measures computed between COVID-19 mortality time series, and GNN implementation. Section IV presents our computational results and some discussion of their relevance. Section V provides our conclusions and some directions for future work.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

The COVID-19 pandemic has been widely examined from different angles, including disease modeling, movement patterns, environmental conditions, and policy effects [1], [2], [3]. A significant portion of research has concentrated on tracking how the virus moved between populations using models of propagation which suffer from lack of empirical validation [4], [5], [6], relationship studies between different factors [7], [8], [9], and network approaches [10], [11], [12]. Some researchers have used theoretical susceptible-infected-recovered disease spread models with some additional mechanisms [13], [14], [15], but in general these works did not carry out extensive validations against real data. Studies have used various statistical and computing methods to examine virus spread [16], [17], [18], including models that track infection patterns and mathematical systems that simulate transmission [19], [20], [18]. Research has also connected virus movement to human travel behaviors using mobile data and transportation information. Other important work has studied how weather conditions and population characteristics affected infection rates, as well as how government measures and vaccines changed transmission. However, most existing research has limitations. Many studies only looked at single countries or combined data from whole regions [21], [22], [23], missing important details about how the virus moved across borders [24], [25], [26]. While some used network approaches, few combined multiple timing measures with machine learning while considering physical distances between places. There is a lack of retrospective statistical studies that consider the available data as it is, trying to figure out what really

happened instead of imposing models disregarding the reality. Some efforts towards the assessment of clustering of countries according to mortality results of the pandemic have been reported [27], [28], [29], but still much work remains to be done in order to achieve an objective regard about the pandemic evolution and its lasting effects.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The analysis utilizes two primary datasets. The first dataset consists of COVID-19 mortality statistics sourced from Our World in Data (OWiD), retrieved on February 14, 2025. This dataset includes daily records from January 1 to December 31, 2020, covering 51 European nations. The key variable of interest is the 7-day smoothed daily deaths per million inhabitants (`new_deaths_per_million`), which was selected to enable standardized comparisons across countries with varying population sizes.

The second dataset consists of a geographic distance matrix constructed specifically for this study. This matrix was generated by calculating pairwise distances between national capital cities based on latitude and longitude coordinates. The resulting 51×51 symmetric matrix contains distance values in kilometers, with diagonal entries set to zero to represent same-country distances. Distance values were normalized to a $[0, 1]$ interval to ensure compatibility with other measures.

B. Color coded maps

Color-coded maps of quartiles represent a powerful tool in epidemiological research for visualizing complex data trends in different geographic regions. These maps separate the data into four equal groups, known as quartiles, and each group is represented by different colors. The darkest shades typically indicate the earliest, most severe or highest values (Q1), while lighter shades represent the latest, mildest or lowest values (Q4). This approach allows researchers to quickly identify patterns, outliers, and regional disparities in the spread and impact of the disease.

C. Similarity measures

1) *Relative dates and peaks of the time series:* We consider for the time series of each country in Europe the following dates: the date of the first COVID-19 case reported, the date of the first COVID-19 death reported, and the date of the greatest peak of deaths in the year 2020. Then, for each pair of countries we compute the number of days that between these events in these countries. The resulting matrices are symmetric and can be interpreted as a kind of propagation time distance between countries. We expect the differences in the dates of the events to be positively correlated with the geographical distance between countries.

2) *Dynamic time warping:* The dynamic time warping (DTW) [30] carries out the optimal dynamic alignment of two signals. First, DTW computes the cost matrix given by the distances between all pairs of signal values. Secondly, DTW searches the path of minimal cost traversing this matrix from

the origin (given by the initial time points) to the final point (given by the last time points of the signals). Formally, given two time series $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_N\}$ and $Y = \{y_1, \dots, y_N\}$, with $x_i, y_j \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the cost matrix is defined as follows:

$$C_{X,Y}(i, j) = \|x_i - y_j\|, \quad (1)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean distance. The DTW finds the path that minimizes the cost of alignment between X and Y by traversing the cost matrix starting from $C_{X,Y}(1, 1)$ and ending in $C_{X,Y}(N, N)$. The algorithm performs a greedy search, where at each step finds the direction of minimal cost for the next matching forward, never going back. The DTW distance can be computed by the following recursive equation: $d_{X,Y}(i, j) = C_{X,Y}(i, j) + \min\{d_{X,Y}(i-1, j-1), d_{X,Y}(i-1, j), d_{X,Y}(i, j-1)\}$. We compute the DTW distance between countries COVID-19 mortality time series. Countries that are closer should have lower DTW than countries that are far away. Thus we expect a positive correlation between DTW distances and geographical distance.

3) *Cross correlation:* The cross-correlation is a measure of similarity of two series as a function of the displacement of one relative to the other. It can be thought of as a sliding dot product or sliding inner-product. For finite discrete time series $X = \{x_n, n = 1, \dots, N\}$ and $Y = \{y_n, n = 1, \dots, N\}$, it can be expressed as:

$$(X \star Y)[n] = \sum_{m=0}^N \bar{X}_m Y_{(m+n)}, \quad (2)$$

where the signals can be padded with zeros to solve boundary condition problems. In this formulation n is the lag, and \bar{X}_m denotes the complex conjugate. In this work we will be interested in the lag value that provides the maximal value of the cross-correlation, i.e. $n^* = \arg \max_n \{(X \star Y)[n]\}$, corresponding to the best rigid alignment between time series. This optimal lag gives information about the propagation of the virus in the sense that countries that are farther away should have longer optimal lags than countries that close geographically. Thus we expect a positive correlation between optimal lags and physical distance.

4) *Wavelet coherence:* The Wavelet Coherence (WC) original definition [31] is based on the Morlet wavelet, defined as follows: $\psi_0(\eta) = \pi^{-1/4} e^{i\omega_0\eta} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\eta^2}$ where ω_0 is frequency, and η is time, both dimensionless. The continuous wavelet transform (CWT) is a convolution of the time series $X = \{x_n, n = 1, \dots, N\}$ with uniform time steps δt with the normalized wavelet for a given scale s :

$$W_n^X(s) = \sqrt{\frac{\delta t}{s}} \sum_{n'=1}^N x_{n'} \psi_0 \left[(n' - n) \frac{\delta t}{s} \right]. \quad (3)$$

The cross wavelet transform (XWT) of two time series $X = \{x_n, n = 1, \dots, N\}$ and $Y = \{y_n, n = 1, \dots, N\}$ is defined as $W^{XY} = W^X W^{Y*}$, where $*$ denotes the complex conjugate. The XWT power is defined as $|W^{XY}|$. The complex argument

of W^{XY} can be interpreted as the local relative phase the time series in time-frequency space.

The wavelet coherence (WC) is defined as

$$R_n^2 = \frac{|S(s^{-1}W_n^{XY}(s))|^2}{S(s^{-1}|W_n^X(s)|^2) \cdot S(s^{-1}|W_n^Y(s)|^2)}, \quad (4)$$

where S is a smoothing operator that is specific to the chosen wavelet. From this definition, wavelet coherence can be interpreted as a localized correlation coefficient in the time/frequency space. For the study in this paper, we consider the norm of the discrete WC as a global measure of the similitude between signals given by the COVID-19 mortality time series. We expect the correlation between WC norm and the geographical distance to be negative, i.e. farther away countries should have smaller coherence than close by countries.

5) *Importance in predictive approaches:* We have considered Linear Regression (LR) and Random Forest (RF) regression [32] in order to build predictive models of the mortality in each country using as regressors the mortality in the remaining countries. The mortality prediction in one country was based on the same day mortality data of the remaining countries. Both approaches provide means to estimate the importance of the input regressors. We use as these importance measures as similarity measure between countries under the assumption that, in case of spatial diffusion of the pathogen, countries that are far away will have lower importance in predicting the deaths in a given country than geographically close countries.

D. Overall processing pipeline

First, we compute the similarities/distances between countries discussed above, obtaining seven symmetric matrices of the same dimensions as the geographical distance matrix between countries. Secondly, we compute the Pearson's, Spearman's, and Kendall's correlation coefficients between each similarity matrix and the geographical distance matrix. These correlation coefficients give us information about the likelihood of the pathogen spatial diffusion hypothesis.

IV. RESULTS

A. Qualitative assessment

The choropleths in the Figure 1 give a qualitative appraisal of the evolution of the pandemic: colors are assigned according to the quartiles (Q1-Q4) of the corresponding measures. Figure 1(a) classifies European countries into quartiles (Q1-Q4) based on the date of their first reported COVID-19 case. Finland, Germany and France appear in the first quartile, while central and smaller countries (e.g. Macedonia, Lithuania, Cyprus) are placed in the last quartile. There is a clear progression from outer to inner countries, reflecting earlier exposure in countries with fewer adjacent countries and the largest in Europe. Some Eastern European countries (e.g., Romania) reported cases earlier than neighboring regions. From this figure the impression is that the emergence of the disease was almost simultaneous with some counties lagging behind,

Fig. 1. Choropleths of the four basic pandemic measures of countries (a) the dates of the first case, (b) the dates of the first death, (c) the dates of the highest mortality peak in 2020, and (d) the mortality relative to the population at the end of the pandemic.

but with little influence of geographical distances. In Figure 1(b) countries are color-coded according to their first reported COVID-19 death. Some countries remain synchronized, but others change their relative order regardless of geographical distances. Figure 1(c) represents the quartiles of the dates of the mortality peak in 2020. The earliest peaks are located in the West of Europe and appear to propagate towards the center, ending with the highest peaks of mortality in the East of the continent, where COVID-19 deaths were reported significantly later in the pandemic timeline. This delay can be attributed to viral spread, different pandemic response timelines, or

variations in death notification practices. Finally, Figure 1(d) stratifies countries according to COVID-19 mortality rates at the end of the pandemic. It can be seen how central-eastern European countries and smaller countries have the highest mortality ratio. Despite early outbreaks, some countries have mid-range mortality (Q2-Q3), possibly due to younger demographics or undercounting deaths. These mortality patterns reflect the healthcare infrastructure of each country (e.g., facilities, demographics) rather than the mere fact of the spread of infection. Cases and deaths followed an inward spread from outer Europe to the more central countries, but mortality final rates did not strictly correspond to the timing of the outbreak. The high mortality in Eastern Europe underscores the role of non-temporal factors (e.g. government, access to health care). However, inconsistent reporting may have skewed quartile rankings across some regions. These visualizations suggest that, although geographic proximity influenced early spread, socioeconomic and political factors determined the ultimate mortality outcomes.

B. Correlation analysis

Figure 2 provides a visual representation of the geographical distance matrix and the mortality similarity/distance matrices computed over the mortality time series of the European countries. Its inspection provides little assurance of the spatial diffusion. Table ?? provides the correlation coefficients between the geographical distance matrix and the mortality similarity/distance matrices. Notice that all correlation coefficients have very low values, meaning an almost complete disconnection of the mortality patterns with the relative distance between countries. In other words, there is no evidence of a pathogen spatial diffusion across Europe. Only the DTW distance has positive correlation coefficient values close to 0.1, which can be interpreted as evidence that some small cluster of countries did have some synchronization in the evolution of the mortality, but that this phenomenon did not extend to the majority of countries.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper examines the hypothesis of the spatial diffusion of the COVID-19 in Europe in the year 2020 from a macroscopic point of view. We do examine the similarity between the mortality patterns of the countries from seven aspects (i.e. date of first case, first death, mortality peak in 2020, the norm of the wavelet coherence, the dynamic time warp distance, the cross correlation optimal lag, and the importance as predictors in Linear Regression and Random Forest models) and compare them with the geographical distance between countries, finding no or very little correlation which does not allow to support the pathogen spatial diffusion hypothesis. These results go against the intuitive general assumption of person to person propagation of the pathogen. Future research should explore the specific mechanisms—such as mobility data or demographic factors—that drove the observed clustering patterns. Additionally, applying this approach to other

global regions or different phases of the pandemic could validate its generalizability and refine its predictiveness.

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Fig. 2. Heat maps of the computed similarity measures extracted from the OWID data. (a) distances between countries, (b) first case date differences, (c) maximum deaths date differences, (d) cross correlation optimal lag, (e) DTW distances, (f) LR importances, (g) RF importances, (h) wavelet coherence magnitude.

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